

EFFECT OF RESIDUAL STRESS ON MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF SiC/Al COMPOSITE

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INTRODUCTION

The residual stress is inevitably generated for fiber reinforced metal composite after heat process such as production or heat treatment, since there is a large difference in thermal expansion between the matrix metal and reinforced fiber. It is widely known that the residual stress has a great influence on many mechanical behaviors of the composite. Therefore, a lot of studies have been reported on theoretical analysis [1-2], experimental measurement [2-3], effects of interfacial reaction [5] and heat treatment on the residual stress [6] and FEM analysis [7-8]. It was clarified that the interfacial strength is related to the residual stress [9-11]. In addition, it was pointed out that the residual stress almost does not have influence on composite strength [12]. However, the effect of the residual stress on the mechanical behavior of the composite has not been clarified during the process of tensile or compressive test.

In this study, the residual stress was generated using heat treatment; sub-zero treatment and pre-loading for unidirectional reinforced SiC/Al composite fabricated by hot press. The residual stress was measured by X-ray analysis. A tensile test was carried out for the SiC/Al composite. Furthermore, the effect of the residual stress on the mechanical behavior of the composite during tensile test was discussed. Meanwhile, the effect of the residual stress was evaluated by the calculation analysis using the rule of mixture (ROM).

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Production and treatment of SiC/Al composite specimen

The matrix material in the present study was A1050 pure aluminum plate with a thickness of 0.2mm. SiC_{CVD} fiber, produced by Textron Specialty Materials (type SCS-2, diameter: 140 μ m), was used as the reinforcement material. SiC/Al composite was fabricated through the following procedure. Firstly, a pure aluminum plate was cut into 30 \times 70mm² pieces, which were then annealed at 573K for 30min in air. In order to arrange the fibers on the aluminum pieces orderly, U-shaped grooves with an interspace of 0.5mm were made on one side of the aluminum pieces by pressing the stainless steel wires (with a diameter of 140 μ m) into the pieces. Secondly, SiC fibers, which were cut into a length of 70mm from the obtained continuous SiC fiber, were put into the grooves on the surface of each aluminum piece, and one more SiC fiber was put into between the fibers afterward. Then one sandwich layer SiC/Al preform was obtained by overlapping another one aluminum piece on that aluminum piece with SiC

Fig.1 A cross section microstructure of SiC/Al composite.

composite having unidirectional three layers of SiC fiber, fiber spacing of about 0.25mm and fiber volume fraction of 9.2% was prepared. Figure 1 gives a microstructure of SiC/Al composite fabricated in the present study. It can be seen that the fibers of three layers almost distribute in the matrix orderly and there are good interfaces.

In order to make the specimens to have the same condition about the surface and the initial residual stress, the surface of the composite obtained from the above hot press process was polished down about 10 μ m using No.320 smoothness of sandpaper. Then the specimens were annealed under the condition of heating temperature of 823K, holding time of 5min and furnace cooling. Also, to obtain the composite specimen having different the residual stress, heat treatment, sub-zero treatment and pre-loading were carried out for the SiC/Al composite. Table 1 lists the treatment processes. In the heat treatment, cooling speed was changed by different cooling method, furnace cooling (sample number I), air-cooling (sample number II) and water quenching (sample number III) after heating to 823K and holding 5min in air. On the other hand, liquid nitrogen (sample number IV) and liquid nitrogen which added ethanol (sample number V) were used as the liquid refrigerant for sub-zero treatment, respectively. The specimens were put into the liquid refrigerant and held 10min, and then returned to room temperature. In the case of pre-loading (sample number VI), the specimen was loaded along the direction of SiC fibers till the load, which make the specimen to give one stress (95.9MPa) of the quarter of the self strength (383.4MPa). According to the pre-experiment, the matrix can reach yield but the damage is not given to the SiC fibers under the above pre-loading.

Measurement of the residual stress and tensile test

The residual stresses of the aluminum matrix along the fiber direction and the right angle direction were measured out by X-ray analysis based on Iso-Inclination method of parallel beam (JDX-3530, JOEL Co. Ltd.) through measuring the diffracted peak from (422) plane of the aluminum matrix at room temperature. The irradiated area was limited on a constant one (20 \times 20mm²) for the all

Table 1 Treatment processes of SiC/Al composite.

Sample number	Treatment process
I	823K \times 5min annealed
II	823K \times 5min air cooling
III	823K \times 5min water quenched
IV	77K \times 10min sub-zero treated
V	176K \times 10min sub-zero treated
VI	Pre-loading (95.9MPa)

fibers. Finally, the sandwich preform of three layers was superimposed and hot pressed into the SiC/Al composite under process condition of temperature 893K, pressure 56MPa and holding time 40min in the atmosphere. SiC/Al

Table 2 Conditions for X-ray stress measurement.

Characteristic X-ray	Cu-K
Tube voltage and current	40kV, 35mA
Measuring method	Para-focusing, -diffractometer
Irradiated area	20mm \times 20mm
Diffraction plane	Al(422)
Counting time (sec)	5.00
Angular interval (deg)	0.08
ψ (deg)	0.00,-19.00,-23.00,-29.00, -34.00,-40.00,-43.00,-45.00

samples by applying plastic tapes to the sample surface. To remove the oxide film on the sample surface, the surface was polished uniformly using No.1500 smoothness of sandpaper before X-ray analysis of the residual stress. Table 2 lists the conditions of X-ray analysis for measuring the residual stress. The residual stress, σ_r was calculated out using equation (1) and (2).

$$\sigma_r = -K M \quad \dots\dots (1)$$

$$K = E \cot \theta_0 / 2(1+\nu) \quad \dots\dots (2)$$

Where K is the stress factor, M is the slope of $2\theta - \sin^2\psi$ diagram, that is, $M = (2\theta) / (\sin^2\psi)$. E is Young's modulus, and ν shows Poisson's ratio. θ represents the diffraction angle of (422) plane of the aluminum matrix. θ_0 represents the diffraction angle of (422) plane when the matrix has no the residual stress. In the present study, the diffraction angle of (422) plane of pure aluminum plate, which was annealed under the condition of temperature 823K and holding time 30min, was substituted for $2\theta_0$ (=137.799 deg). Young's modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν were substituted by those of the aluminum matrix, 69.5GPa and 0.33, respectively.

A tensile test was carried out for the SiC/Al composite having different residual stresses. The tensile specimens were cut into 70mm in length, 6mm in width and 1mm in thickness from the composite, as there exist 39 SiC fibers in a tensile specimen. Tensile test was done at room temperature in a screw driven constant crosshead tensile testing machine (Shimadzu, AG-5000ES) under a constant tensile speed of 0.05mm/min and a gauge length of 10mm. A strain gauge was applied to the center along tensile direction of each tensile specimen. In order to understand the fiber strength in the SiC/Al composite, the fibers were extracted by dissolving the matrix with 10%NaOH water solution, and then a tensile test was carried out for the fibers. Further, to obtain the parameters of mechanical property of the aluminum matrix, a tensile test was done for pure aluminum specimen, which had the same dimension with the composite specimen, and was under the same fabrication and treatment process with sample number I shown in Table 1. Also, the gauge length was 10mm for the tensile specimens of the extracted fiber and the pure aluminum. Tabs of aluminum pieces were set to both the ends of all tensile specimens.

CALCULATION TECHNIQUE USING THE RULE OF MIXTURE

In the present study, the rule of mixture (ROM) was improved to evaluate the effect of the residual stress on the mechanical behavior during tensile test of the composite. Firstly, it was supposed that the residual stresses of both the matrix and fiber follow ROM. It was presumed that relationship between the stress and strain of the matrix agrees to n -power hardening rule. The residual strain of the matrix and fiber, ϵ_{fr} and ϵ_{mr} can be calculated out by ROM using the measured matrix residual stress, σ_{mr} as follows.

$$\sigma_{fr} V_f + \sigma_{mr} (1 - V_f) = 0 \quad \dots\dots(3) \quad \text{and} \quad E_f \epsilon_{fr} V_f + \sigma_{mr} (1 - V_f) = 0 \quad \dots\dots(4)$$

Then the fiber residual strain:

$$\epsilon_{fr} = -\{\sigma_{mr} (1 - V_f) / E_f V_f\} \quad \dots\dots(5)$$

And the matrix residual strain:

$$\epsilon_{mr} = \sigma_{mr} / E_m \quad (\sigma_{mr} < \sigma_y) \quad \dots\dots(6-1)$$

$$\epsilon_{mr} = (\sigma_{mr} / K)^{1/n} \quad (\sigma_{mr} > \sigma_y) \quad \dots\dots(6-2)$$

Table 3 Parameters for calculating by rule of mixture.

σ_y (MPa)	E_m (GPa)	K (MPa)	n	E_f (GPa)	V_f (%)
23.2	69.5	192.3	0.262	421	9.2

Then stress of the composite having residual stress during tensile test can be evaluated by adding the residual strains of the matrix and fiber to ROM as shown in equation (7-1) and (7-2), and making the composite strain, ϵ_c to increase with a step, 0.001% till 1.0%.

$$\sigma_c = E_f V_f (\epsilon_c + \epsilon_{fr}) + E_m (1 - V_f) (\epsilon_c + \epsilon_{mr}) \quad (\sigma_m < \sigma_y) \quad \dots\dots(7-1)$$

$$\sigma_c = E_f V_f (\epsilon_c + \epsilon_{fr}) + (1 - V_f) \{K (\epsilon_c + \epsilon_{mr})^n\} \quad (\sigma_m > \sigma_y) \quad \dots\dots(7-2)$$

Here E is elastic modulus, ϵ and σ show strain and stress, respectively. Also, subscript f, m, c, y and r mean fiber, matrix, composite, yield and residual, respectively. Tension and compression are indicated

by marking a plus and a minus sign, respectively. Parameters for the calculation technique using ROM are shown in Table 3.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Residual stress of SiC/Al composite

Figure 2 shows diagrams of 2θ - $\sin^2\psi$ for typical the three processes. From the figure, it can be seen that there is a good linear relationship between 2θ and $\sin^2\psi$. The residual stress was calculated by substituting the slope of 2θ - $\sin^2\psi$ diagram to equation (1) as the above mentioned. Table 4 gives the residual stresses along the fiber direction (0°) and the right angle direction (90°) for each process. The composites having different residual stresses were obtained using the present treatment processes. The residual stress along the fiber direction is larger than that of the right angle direction. Also, it is noticeable that the residual stress of the same samples is over yield stress (about 30MPa) of the aluminum matrix. In the cases of heat and

Fig.2 Diagrams of 2θ - $\sin^2\psi$

Table 4 Treatment processes and residual stress of SiC/Al composite.

Sample number	Treatment process	Residual stress (MPa)	
		0°	90°
I	823K \times 5min annealed	11.2 ± 2.2	3.9 ± 5.3
II	823K \times 5min air cooling	20.6 ± 1.1	4.7 ± 0.7
III	823K \times 5min water quenched	41.8 ± 3.1	12.4 ± 4.1
IV	77K \times 10min sub-zero treated	-35.5 ± 1.6	-17.7 ± 2.1
V	176K \times 10min sub-zero treated	-18.8 ± 3.3	-5.4 ± 1.1
VI	Pre-loading (95.9MPa)	-34.3 ± 3.2	1.5 ± 0.8

sub-zero treatments, it is easy to understand simply that the residual stress originates in different thermal expansion behavior of the fiber and matrix. On the other hand, the residual stress occurs due to plastic deformation of the matrix and elastic recovery of the fiber in the case of pre-loading.

It can be understand that there is a distribution for the residual stress along the thickness direction of the composite. In the present study, the distribution of the residual stress was examined by polishing down about $10\mu\text{m}$ from the surface and measuring the residual stress repeatedly. The distribution of residual stress for sample number IV is shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the residual stress increases along the thickness direction. In addition, it was confirmed that the advancing depth of X-ray is about $75\mu\text{m}$ in the present condition. Therefore, it can be understood that the value of the

Fig.3 Distribution of residual stress along vertical direction of the surface (sample number: IV).

residual stress in the present study is a mean value to about 75 μ m thickness from the measurement surface.

Effect of the residual stress on mechanical behavior

Figure 4 presents a stress-strain curve of the SiC/Al composite from tensile test. There is a point on the curve, at which the slope had a precise changing due to the matrix yield during tensile test of the composite. To find the effect of the residual stress on mechanical behavior during tensile test, the composite stresses were read out from strain-stress curve at the matrix yield, the strain of 0.1%, 0.2%, 0.5% and the broken point for the each process. Relationship between the residual stress and these composite stresses is shown in Fig.5. It is interesting that the residual stress has a great influence in the composite stress when the composite stress is lower. However, the influence goes down with the increase of composite stress and almost does not appear at the broken point of the composite (σ_{cu}). Besides stress-strain curves of SiC/Al composites were obtained from ROM calculation analysis as mentioned earlier. For example, a stress-strain curve from ROM calculation analysis is shown in Fig.6. The slope changing during the tensile test (Fig.4) was well simulated by the present analysis using ROM. As the same way, the composite stresses were read out from strain-stress curve, which was calculated out from the present analysis using ROM at the same strain points with Fig.5. The results are shown in Fig.7. From this figure, it can be known that the same trend as the experiment (Fig.5) appears, although there is a little difference at stress value. The present calculation analysis is a simple and effective way to examine the effect of residual stress on mechanical behavior of the composite. The slopes of the relationship between the residual stress and tensile stress of the composite as shown in Fig.5 and Fig.7 can be used as a parameter indicating the extent of the influence of the residual stress. Table 5 lists the slopes. Although the values from the experiment and the calculation analysis have a difference, the absolute values decrease with increase of tensile stress of the

Fig.4 A stress-strain curve of SiC/Al composite from tensile test (sample number: IV).

Fig.5 Relationship between residual stress and tensile stresses of SiC/Al composite during tensile test.

Fig.6 A stress-strain curve of SiC/Al composite from ROM (sample number: IV).

Fig.7 Relationship between residual stress and tensile stresses of SiC/Al composite from ROM.

with increasing the stress level of the composite, almost does not appear for the composite strength.

As shown in Fig.4, E_1 and E_2 express Young's modulus of the composite before and after the matrix yield, respectively. Relationship between the residual stress and Young's modulus of the composite is shown in Fig.8. It is clear that the residual stress does not influence Young's modulus of the composite.

CONCLUSIONS

The residual stress has a great influence in the composite stress when the composite stress is lower. The influence goes down with increase of the composite stress and almost does not appear at the broken point of the composite. The effects of the residual stress on Young's modulus of the composite do not appear. The present calculation analysis using ROM is a simple and effective way to evaluate the effect of residual stress on mechanical behavior of the composite during tensile test.

REFERENCE

- [1] H. J. Chun, I. M. Daniel and S. C. Wooh, Composites Engineering, **5-4**(1995), 425-436.
- [2] C. Zhang and H. Y. Yeh, Int. J. Solids Struct., **35-5/6**(1998), 157-477.
- [3] T. Ericsson, A. Ohlsson and C. Persson, Advance X-ray Analysis, **36**(1993), 461-472.
- [4] J. Lu and D. Reirant, J. Strain Anal. Eng. Des., **33-2**(1998), 127-136.
- [5] K. Debray, E. Martin and J. M. Quenisset, J. Compos. Mater., **33-4**(1999), 325-350.
- [6] Yun LU and H. Fukunaga, Proc. ICRS-3, Japan, 1991, Vol.1, 40-45.
- [7] J. F. Durodola and B. Derby, Acta Metall. Mater., **42-5**(1994), 1525-1534.
- [8] P. Rangaswamy and N. Jayaraman, Computer Engineering, 1993, P.483-497.
- [9] R. A. Shatwell, Mater. Sci. Eng. A, **A259-2**(1999), 162-170.
- [10] S. G. Warriar, P. Rangaswamy, M. A. M. Bourke and S. Krishnamurthy, Mater Sci., Eng. A, **A259-2**(1999), 220-227.
- [11] Jiang Xiaoyu and Kong Xiangan, Compos. Sci. Technol., **59-5**(1999), 635-642.
- [12] D. B. Zahl and R. M. Mcmeeking, Acta Metall. Mater., **39-6**(1991), 1117-1122.

Table 5 Slopes of relationship between residual stress and tensile stress.

Tensile stress	Experiment	Rule of mixture
cy	-0.57	-1.46
0.5	-0.13	-0.84
cu	-0.08	0.16

composite. From the above results, it can be concluded that the effect of the residual stress on tensile stress of the composite is limited at a lower stress level, and goes down

Fig.8 Relationship between residual stress and Young's modulus of SiC/Al composite.